
Teachers Burnout: Causes, Impact and Conciliations

Divya

Ph.D Scholar, Department of Education, Faculty of Education S.V.S.U. (Meerut U.P.) Pin Code:-250005

Email:- divyaasharma1112@gmail.com

Dr. Indira Singh

Prof. & Head, Department of Education, Faculty of Education S.V.S.U. (Meerut U.P.) Pin Code:-

250005, Email:- indirasingh285@gmail.com

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16785077>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 17-07-2025

Published: 10-08-2025

Keywords:

Teachers Burnout, NEP 2020, Work Engagement, Occupational Stress, Emotional Exhaustion and Coping Strategies.

ABSTRACT

As we know burnout is a highly growing problem across the world whether in the students, teachers, parents, doctors, or all the fields. And teacher burnout is one of the most rapidly growing in society. Teachers' burnout impacts on their psychological health which affects their performance in the job, the ability of providing the good quality education they provide to their students and also impact their relationships with their students and colleagues due to emotional exhaustion. This review paper collects data by gathering information from 2000 to 2025 studies, which are especially focused on recent years or we may say after covid 19 health crises. This review paper describes what is the meaning of teachers burnout, what are the causes of teachers burnout, how it impacts their teaching and their relations with students. It also focuses on the situation of teachers after publishing National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in India. This paper wishes to provide help to policy makers, school management and leaders or educators for making better understanding about teacher burnout and taking strict steps towards reducing it and providing

Introduction

Teaching is not only just a duty\job; it is a vocation\profession which needs full dedication towards their work, it includes mental strength and emotional involvement towards the dedication of their responsibilities. Teachers are responsible for shaping the future of their students and nation. They help in guiding them in their learning process and also helping them in growing them and making them responsible and socially accepted people in the society as well as emotionally strong. However teachers face a lot of challenges mainly in the last few years after the covid 19 pandemics (health crises 2020). Due to this it increases the teachers workload, focused shift towards digital teaching and lack of support from organizations or institutions (Moorhouse et al., 2021; Agyapong et al., 2022). All of these things create a pressure on teachers and lead towards what we call teachers burnout.

Teacher burnout is a situation where educators or teachers feel psychologically, mentally and emotionally exhausted. It may develop a negative attitude towards their work and their profession and stop the feeling of being effective and creative as a teacher. Very first time the idea of burnout was explained by Maslach and Jackson in 1981, they describe that it has mainly three parts or dimensions. Which are: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced sense of personal achievements.

In today's time period teachers burnout is a very hot and trending topic and it is also very important because every second teacher facing this situation which directly impact on their personal health and when they are facing the feeling of burned out, it doesn't solely impact on them but they also impact on students which they are engaged with them, school in they are working and the overall teaching and learning environment (Chang, 2009; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017). As we know after the introduction of New Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in India they may have brought many fruitful changes in the education system but they also increased the responsibilities of the teachers (Kumar & Yadav, 2024). The reforms are good but they need to be implemented in a proper way with the full support of teachers so that they do not increase their burnout and reduce their stress.

This paper will try to explain this points:

- What is teacher burnout?
- How has it been studied?

- What are the causes of teacher burnout?
- What is its effect on education?
- What Precautions are taken by school to prevent it?
- How does the education system of India respond to it?

2. Methodology

This paper is rooted with the thematic and narrative review. The paper analyses different studies then encapsulates the outcomes and findings from that, and after that well organized the information into understandable ways and themes. This paper is not just solely focused on the numbers or statistics part of the research, instead it focuses on the mother who gives a broader and deeper understanding of the research problem (Montgomery & Rupp, 2005).

The database used by the researcher for this type of relevant articles:

- Google Scholar
- Scopus
- Science Direct
- PubMed
- ERIC

Things are included:-

1. Studies only included which are published between 2000 to 2025.
2. Study articles only which are peer reviewed.
3. Studies included which are related to school teachers (not college or university).
4. Mainly focused on those studies which focused on reasons for burnout, their impact on all over the school system, and the solutions of the burnout (Brunsting et al., 2014).

From 2000 to 2025, 110 studies were found which are related to teacher burnout and 50 researches were chosen after scrutinizing their topic, abstract and full texts. These studies were divided into the main topics such as meaning, reasons, impact, solutions and the research which is only Indian specific research.

3. Conceptual Framework for Teachers Burnout

Teacher burnout has basically three main dimensions, which are as:

1. **Emotional Exhaustion:** Teachers feel due to the mental and physical drain from high stress from a long time.
2. **Depersonalization:** the feeling of disconnection from students and other members and may develop anxiety, stress and indifferent attitude.
3. **Reduced Personal Accomplishment:** The feeling that they are not creating something new and also lose in their confidence and the interest in their teaching abilities (Maslach & Jackson, 1981; Maslach et al., 2001).

Here are some models of burnout that help us to make more clarification about that.

Maslach burnout inventory (MBI): This is the very first model which is used for measuring the burnout among teachers. This model was developed by Maslach and Jackson in 1981 (Maslach et al., 2001).

Job Demands Resource (JD-R) Model: this model refers to that teachers face burnout when the demands of the jobs are very high in comparison the resources for that which creates stress and teachers have to manage (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

Transactional Model of Stress and Coping: In this model burnout depends on how teachers see the burnout and how they try to cope with it (Friedman, 2000).

4. Causes of Teachers Burnout

Teacher burnout is not the only cause. It is a collection of many factors which work together and form burnout.

- **Individualized Factor:** This factor is related to lack of personal well being, personality traits, family care and responsibility. A teacher who is perfectionist but due to the lack of self-confidence may suffer from burnout very fast (Aloe et al., 2014).
- **Organizational Factor:** The environment of the organization may create burnout, the factors may include overwork load with insufficient facilities, over crowded classes, poor leadership, unstructured goals etc (Chang, 2009; Brouwers & Tomic, 2000).

- **Systematic Factors:** In this the policies of the government and higher authority, culture of educational reforms, lack of freedom and the pressure of management on teachers “do more with less” (Farber, 2000; Jain & Sharma, 2023).
- **Technological Factor:** During and after the covid 19 teachers had to face a new task in their teaching process which creates stress- adopting technology in the teaching, online digital tools and increasing the working hours without any extra support by management or authority (Moorhouse et al., 2021).

5. Impact and Effect of Teachers Burnout

It doesn't not only impact teachers individually, but it also impacts on the factors which are related to teachers.

- **Impact on Teacher Individually:** Foremost it affects teachers health, problems like- stress, anxiety, depression and insomnia. They effects teachers' mental health as well as emotional and physical too, due to which many of the teachers quit their profession at an early stage (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017; Santoro, 2018).
- **Impact on Students:** If teachers are burned-out its impacts on their teaching skills which affects students learning, they become less enthusiastic which leads to low achievement and low motivation (Hakanen et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2021).
- **Impact on School:** Due to burnout school had to face teachers absenteeism increases day by day . They may have to struggle with keeping good teachers in their school and it also affects the overall learning environment and results of the school as well as the image of the school in the society (Prilleltensky et al., 2016).

6. Copying Mechanism and Interventions:

There are several levels which help teachers and students to address burnout and help in overcoming it.

- **At the Personal and Individual Level:**
 - Practicing yoga, meditation, pranayamas and mindfulness.
 - Taking short breaks from long hours of working for self care and relaxation.
 - Building a feeling of cooperation and support system among teachers (Lavy & Eshet, 2018).

- **At the school and organizational Level:**

- Provide a time for proper planning for their work and as well provide the sufficient resources to them.
- Encourage teachers, principals and administrative staff for open and proper communication for the smooth functioning of the organisation.
- Providing the opportunity for the professional development programs that includes psychological training for mental health (Collie et al., 2012).

- **At the Policy Level:**

- When the government policies are framed they should keep in mind the health and well being of the teacher because a healthy teacher provides quality education.
- NEP 2020 stresses more focus on the training and development of the teachers but the reality is so different it needs the implementation on the ground level (Kumar & Yadav, 2024).

7. Indian Context

In India there is little research on teacher burnout in comparison to western countries. So the challenges are very real in nature:

- Teach a large number of students due to over crowded classes.
- Basically our Indian education system is more focused on examination and completion of the syllabus which creates pressure on teachers.
- Government school teachers face a problem of lack of teaching aids. They didn't utilize their full calabura and skill for giving quality education.
- During and after the covid 19 teachers had to face the pressure of online teaching which adds the extra work (Singh & Mishra, 2020; Jain & Sharma, 2023).

The New Education Policy (NEP 2020) has brought new light in the lives of teachers but they need the extra support to implement at the ground level. Indian researchers have the need to understand the cultural differences and causes of burnout and they have to develop the local solution of their problems according to the culture from which they belong to.

8. Gaps in Literature

Some areas are still untouched and need research.

- Need for longitudinal studies to see how it grows and reduces over time (Montgomery & Rupp, 2005).

- To see the impact of online teaching on psychological health (Moorhouse et al., 2021).
- Need work for finding the relationship between teachers burnout and teachers competency or work engagement (Zhang et al., 2021).
- Needed more indian studies which focuses on the teachers burnout on school level (Kumar & Yadav, 2024).

9. Directions for future

- This is the responsibility of the scholars and researchers to take it seriously and work on it for finding the solutions (Blömeke et al., 2022).
- Researchers try to use mixed method research for making better understanding of the issue faced by teachers (Brunsting et al., 2014).
- Work on developing the Indian standardize tools for measuring and evaluating burnout (Jain & Sharma, 2023).
- Train school management, leaders and administration to find the issues and provide support for the struggling teachers (Parker et al., 2012).

10. Conclusion

Teacher burnout is a very significant problem in today's era and this increases day by day. It doesn't not only affect teachers only, they also affect those who are attached with it and those to whom they serve whether it's their family, students and institutes. There are so many causes which create burnout in teachers. Such as over work load, poor working conditions and relation with their colleague, stress, anxiety and policy changes. Thus papers show that the problem of burnout increases day by day and its need for immediate solutions and attention. It's the time to think about the health and well being of the teachers as it is directly related to the part of educational success, because if teachers are not healthy they affect the learners learning with whom they are attached and servers. If we provide them support ,psychological peace, timely training and development programs so they feel respect and care which develops the feeling of empowered teaching roles.

References

- Agyapong, V. I., Osei, A., & Farren, C. (2022). Burnout and mental health in teachers post-COVID. *Psychiatry Research*, 307, 114332. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36078422/>

- Aloe, A. M., Amo, L. C., & Shanahan, M. E. (2014). Classroom management self-efficacy and burnout: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 26(1), 101–126. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-013-9244-0>
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2007). The Job Demands–Resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), 309–328. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940710733115>
- Blömeke, S., Olsen, R. V., & Suhl, U. (2022). Teachers’ professional competence and burnout: A cross-country analysis. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 112, 103640. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=3305920>
- Brouwers, A., & Tomic, W. (2000). A longitudinal study of teacher burnout and perceived self-efficacy in classroom management. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 16(2), 239–253. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(99\)00057-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(99)00057-8)
- Brunsting, N. C., Sreckovic, M. A., & Lane, K. L. (2014). Special education teacher burnout: A synthesis of research from 1979 to 2013. *Education and Treatment of Children*, 37(4), 681–711. <https://doi.org/10.1353/etc.2014.0032>
- Chang, M. L. (2009). An appraisal perspective of teacher burnout: Examining the emotional work of teachers. *Educational Psychology Review*, 21(3), 193–206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-009-9106-y>
- Collie, R. J., Shapka, J. D., & Perry, N. E. (2012). School climate and social–emotional learning: Predicting teacher stress, job satisfaction, and teaching efficacy. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 104(4), 1189–1204. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029356>
- Evers, W. J., Tomic, W., & Brouwers, A. (2004). Burnout among teachers: Students’ and teachers’ perceptions compared. *School Psychology International*, 25(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034304043670>
- Farber, B. A. (2000). Treatment strategies for different types of teacher burnout. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 56(5), 675–689. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4679\(200005\)56:5<675::AID-JCLP9>3.0.CO;2-D](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4679(200005)56:5<675::AID-JCLP9>3.0.CO;2-D)
- Friedman, I. A. (2000). Burnout in teachers: Shattered dreams of impeccable professional performance. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 56(5), 595–606. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4679\(200005\)56:5<595::AID-JCLP2>3.0.CO;2-Q](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4679(200005)56:5<595::AID-JCLP2>3.0.CO;2-Q)
- Hakanen, J. J., Bakker, A. B., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2006). Burnout and work engagement among teachers. *Journal of School Psychology*, 43(6), 495–513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2005.11.001>

- Jain, R., & Sharma, V. (2023). Mental health and burnout among Indian school teachers: The post-pandemic scenario. *Indian Journal of Education and Psychology, 19*(1), 51–60.
- Kumar, V., & Yadav, S. (2024). Teacher burnout in the context of NEP 2020: Challenges and policy implications. *Journal of Indian Educational Research, 14*(2), 67–78.
- Kyriacou, C. (2001). Teacher stress: Directions for future research. *Educational Review, 53*(1), 27–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131910120033628>
- Lavy, S., & Eshet, R. (2018). Spiral effects of teachers' emotions and emotion regulation strategies. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 73*, 90–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.03.004>
- Maslach, C., & Jackson, S. E. (1981). The measurement of experienced burnout. *Journal of Occupational Behavior, 2*(2), 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.4030020205>
- Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Leiter, M. P. (2001). Job burnout. *Annual Review of Psychology, 52*, 397–422. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.397>
- Montgomery, C., & Rupp, A. A. (2005). A meta-analysis for exploring the diverse causes and consequences of teacher burnout. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 21*(7), 715–734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2005.05.008>
- Moorhouse, B. L., Wong, K. M., & Ho, L. (2021). Blended synchronous teaching and teacher burnout: A longitudinal study. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 107*, 103458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103458>
- Parker, P. D., Martin, A. J., Colmar, S., & Liem, G. A. (2012). Teachers' workplace well-being: Exploring a process model of goal orientation, coping behavior, engagement, and burnout. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 28*(4), 503–513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2012.01.001>
- Prilleltensky, I., Neff, M., & Bessell, A. (2016). Teacher stress: What it is, why it's important, how it can be alleviated. *Theory Into Practice, 55*(2), 104–111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405841.2016.1148986>
- Richards, J. (2012). Teacher stress and coping strategies: A national snapshot. *The Educational Forum, 76*(3), 299–316. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131725.2012.682837>
- Santoro, D. A. (2018). *Demoralized: Why teachers leave the profession they love and how they can stay*. Harvard Education Press.
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and engagement. *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 25*(3), 293–315. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.248>

- Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2017). Teacher stress and burnout: Relations to school context, job satisfaction, and motivation. *Social Psychology of Education, 20*(2), 223–248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-017-9384-0>
- Singh, B., & Mishra, S. (2020). Burnout and work-life imbalance among Indian school teachers. *Indian Journal of Health and Wellbeing, 11*(2), 101–108.
- Vandenberghe, R., & Huberman, A. M. (1999). *Understanding and preventing teacher burnout: A sourcebook of international research and practice*. Cambridge University Press.
- Watt, H. M., & Richardson, P. W. (2008). Motivation, perceptions, and aspirations concerning teaching as a career for different types of beginning teachers. *Learning and Instruction, 18*(5), 408–428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2008.06.002>
- Zhang, Q., Yin, H., & Huang, S. (2021). Testing a multi-level model of work engagement, teacher burnout, and student outcomes. *International Journal of Educational Research, 105*, 101715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2020.101715>